

TERMINAL RISE VELOCITY OF VARIOUS BUBBLE SIZES IN A TUBE AND AN ANNULAR SPACE THROUGH A VISCOUS LIQUID

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ABSTRACT

The terminal rise velocity of various bubble sizes rising through a viscous liquid (480 cP) has been experimentally determined in a vertical tube and in a concentric vertical annulus. The bubble sizes ranges from cap bubble to Taylor bubble. The tube inside diameter is 76.2 mm. The annular geometry is made from a 25.4 mm outside diameter rod placed concentrically inside the tube. The rise velocity was measured using a high-speed video camera (500 fps) and digital image processing. For the tube, it was found that the rise velocity of a Taylor bubble could be predicted with reliability using the equations available in the literature. For cap bubbles, no previous works were found that covered the parameters of the present study. Thus, unbounded media equations were used, leading this to significant errors in the rise velocity calculation. Also, the bubble kinematics in annular geometry with viscous liquids is still an open subject. Some suggestions are offered which can be used as a method to estimate the rise velocity of cap bubbles in tubes with viscous liquids and cap and Taylor bubbles in annular spaces.

1. INTRODUCTION

The terminal rise velocity of a single cap bubble has been studied by Peebles and Garber [1], Grace and Harrison [2], Bhaga and Weber [3], Wegener and Parlange [4] and by numerous other investigators.

For small bubbles, almost perfect spherical because of the dominant effect of surface tension on their shape, Stokes' solution provides a reasonably accurate description of the rise velocity,

$$u_{\infty}^{sp} = \frac{2g(\rho_l - \rho_g)R_b^2}{9\mu_l} \quad (1)$$

On the other hand, when the bubbles are very large, the effects of surface tension and viscosity are negligible and the rise velocity is given by the equation of Davies and Taylor [5]:

$$u_{\infty} = \frac{2}{3}(gR_c)^{1/2}.$$

This equation can be approximately expressed in terms of R_b [9]:

$$u_{\infty} = 1.00(gR_b)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

For the conditions of the present study the Eq. 3 developed by Peebles and Garber [1] can be used to predict the terminal rise velocity of a cap bubble rising in a low viscosity liquid in an infinite media.

$$u_{\infty} = 1.18 \left[\frac{\sigma g}{\rho_l} \right]^{0.25} \quad (3)$$

Harmathy [6] suggested that a better value for the constant (1.18) of the Eq. 3 is 1.53. Equation 3 yields satisfactory predictions if not applied to very small ($E\ddot{o} = 4\rho_l g R_b^2 / \sigma < 1$) bubbles.

For bubbles and drops rising or falling freely in infinite media Clift *et al.* [7] prepared a generalized graphical correlation in terms of Eötvös number $E\ddot{o}$; Morton number ($M = g\mu_l^4 / \rho_l \sigma^3$); and Reynolds number ($Re = 2\rho_l u_{\infty} R_b / \mu_l$), which may be used to estimate terminal velocities and shape regimes. Although more accurate predictive correlations are available [7].

Bhaga and Weber [3] presented a regime shape map where the variation of Re versus $E\ddot{o}$ with lines of constant M is shown. A number of shape regimes and the transition lines between regimes are also shown on the plot.

Jamialahmadi *et al.* [8] developed a correlation (Eq. 4) for the prediction of terminal bubble rise velocity, covering a wide range of bubble sizes:

$$u_{\infty} = \frac{u_{\infty}^{sp} u_{\infty}^w}{\sqrt{(u_{\infty}^{sp})^2 + (u_{\infty}^w)^2}} \quad (4)$$

where:

$$u_{\infty}^w = \sqrt{\frac{2\sigma}{d_e(\rho_l + \rho_g)} + \frac{gd_e}{2}} \quad (5)$$

and u_{∞}^{sp} is given by Eq. 1.

Eq. 4 was developed covering the following range of liquid physical properties: density from 720 kg/m³ to 1040 kg/m³; viscosity from 0.233 mPa.s to 59 mPa.s and superficial tension from 0.0725 N/m to 0.022 N/m. The effects of gas physical properties on the bubbles rise velocity can be neglected, as long as $\rho_l \gg \rho_g$ and $\mu_l \gg \mu_g$.

When a bubble rises in a finite vessel, its velocity is generally lower than in an infinite medium. In a tube of diameter D , the ratio of the bubble velocity u to the velocity in an infinite medium u_{∞} can be expressed as a function of d_e/D , where $d_e = 2R_b$.

Wallis [9] has derived the following relations for bubbles rising in a cylindrical column based on Collin's work [10]:

$$\frac{d_e}{D} < 0.125 \quad \frac{u}{u_{\infty}} = 1 \quad (6)$$

$$0.125 < \frac{d_e}{D} < 0.6 \quad \frac{u}{u_{\infty}} = 1.13e^{-(d_e/D)} \quad (7)$$

$$0.6 < \frac{d_e}{D} \quad \frac{u}{u_{\infty}} = 0.496 \left(\frac{d_e}{D} \right)^{-1/2} \quad (8)$$

The relations above (Eq. 6-8) are still up-to-date and have been recently used by Krishna *et al.* [11].

The case of a large cylindrical gas bubble rising in a tube containing a non-viscous liquid has been treated theoretically by Dumitrescu (1943) [9] and Davies and Taylor [5]. Both concluded that the rise velocity depends only on the Froude number ($Fr = u^2/(gD)$) having this a constant value, where u denotes the terminal velocity of rise of the bubble in a vertical tube of diameter D . Dumitrescu's theoretical Fr was 0.123 and Davies and Taylor [5] estimated a value of 0.108. Dumitrescu made a series of careful experiments with cylindrical air bubbles rising in water in tubes of large diameter yielding a Fr of 0.119. This is also the value obtained in the experiments done by White and Beardmore [12]. These authors developed a graphical correlation for predicting the rise velocity of cylindrical gas bubbles in liquids in vertical tubes in terms of Fr , $E\ddot{o}$ and M . This correlation is valid for $E\ddot{o} < 10^3$ and $M < 10^6$. Following the literature usage, this type of large, cylindrical bubble will be termed Taylor bubble.

Brown [13] proposed a flow mechanism model for the movement of Taylor bubbles through stagnant liquid in a tube. This model takes into account the effect of liquid viscosity on the film hydrodynamics surrounding the bubble while retaining the concept of potential flow at the nose which has proven

successful for low viscosity liquids [5]. Brown's equations are [13]:

$$u = 0.496\sqrt{gR} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 2NR}}{NR} \right)} \quad (9)$$

where

$$N = \sqrt[3]{14.5 \frac{\rho_l^2 g}{\mu_l^2}} \quad (10)$$

The applicability limits of Eq. 9 were established empirically as:

Surface tension,

$$\frac{\rho_l g R^2}{\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 2NR}}{NR} \right)^2 > 5.0 \quad (11)$$

Viscosity,

$$NR > 30. \quad (12)$$

Wallis [9] proposed a general correlation for Taylor bubble rise velocity in terms of all the relevant variables:

$$u = k \left[\frac{gD(\rho_l - \rho_g)}{\rho_l} \right]^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

and

$$k = 0.345 \left(1 - e^{-0.01N_f/0.345} \right) \left(1 - e^{(337 - E\ddot{o})/n} \right) \quad (14)$$

where N_f is the dimensionless inverse viscosity number:

$$N_f = \frac{[D^3 g(\rho_l - \rho_g)\rho_l]^{1/2}}{\mu_l} \quad (15)$$

n is a function of N_f and takes on the following values:

$$\begin{aligned} N_f > 250 & \quad n = 10 \\ 18 < N_f < 250 & \quad n = 69N_f^{-0.35} \\ N_f < 18 & \quad n = 25. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

2. EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

The experimental set up is shown in Fig. 1. It consists of a transparent acrylic round pipe column with an inside diameter of 76.2 mm and a total height of 2.5 m. An acrylic box is connected at the column bottom. The box has a hemispherical cup held above an injection nozzle. This nozzle is connected to a syringe by means of a capillary tubing. To obtain the desired bubble volume, the air is injected repeatedly with as many syringe strokes as necessary. The air will be trapped by the downward facing cup. The bubble is released by inverting the cup. This mechanism allowed the formation of a wide range of bubble sizes, from small ones (0.8 cm^3) up to Taylor bubbles (until 300 cm^3). A second mechanism was used to form even larger Taylor bubbles, from 300 up to 1400 cm^3 . This device is shown in Fig. 1, which replaces the transparent box. It consists of a 3 inches ball valve, a cylindrical reservoir and a drain. To form a bubble, the ball valve is closed in order to separate the liquid in the bubble formation section from the liquid in the column. Then, a desired volume of liquid is drained from the reservoir. Finally, the bubble is released by opening the valve.

The concentric annulus was formed introducing a 25.4 mm rod inside the pipe. This rod is held fixed at the ends by means of proper retainers.

To measure the rise velocity, the traveling bubble is recorded with a high speed video camera NAC HSV 1000, which acquires 500 frames per second. The frames were digitized with a PCI-1408 National Instruments image acquisition board. The image processing was done using the IMAQ Vision package for LabView. The video technique used for determining bubble velocities yields an error of $\pm 4\%$ for the slower velocities and $\pm 2\%$ for the highest velocities.

The fluids used in the experiments were machinery oil and air. Oil physical properties are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical properties of the test liquid.

Temperature (°C)	Density (kg/m^3)	Viscosity (Pa.s)	Surface tension with air (mN/m)
20	879.8	0.4827	31.5
25	876.6	0.3452	31.4
30	873.0	0.2508	31.1
35	870.3	0.1830	30.9
40	-	0.1373	30.7

More details of the experimental apparatus and procedures can be found elsewhere [14].

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of experimental apparatus.

3. RESULTS

Rise velocity of Taylor bubbles in a circular pipe

The rise velocity of four Taylor bubble sizes was measured in a circular pipe. These measured values were corrected to compensate the air expansion of the bubble using the Eq. 17. The results are shown in Table 2.

The measured velocity u' determined from the bubble movement relative to the tube is the sum of the velocity of the cap relative to the undisturbed liquid above the bubble, u , and the bulk movement of the cap and liquid due to the expansion of the bubble. To correct the data for bubble expansion White and Beardmore [12] derived the next expression:

$$u = u'(1 - \rho_l g l / P_A). \quad (17)$$

Table 2. Experimental rise velocity of Taylor bubbles in a pipe.

Injected air volume ^a (cm ³)	Length (mm)	Experimental velocity, mm/s	
		Measured ± 8	Corrected ^b
1400	430	279	269
250	100	277	275
200	80	270	268
100	50	272	271

^a Absolute pressure 88.5 kPa. Test temperature 22.0 °C.

^b Experimental velocity corrected by air expansion effect.

As can be seen in Table 2, the rise velocity is independent of the bubble length, as has been established by other investigators [5,12]. Moreover, the measured velocity is slightly higher than the corrected velocity and the difference increases with the bubble size as expected from air expansion. The conditions of the present study yield an average rise velocity of a Taylor bubble in a pipe of 271 mm/s.

To predict the rise velocity of a Taylor bubble the correlations of Brown [13] (Eq. 9) and Wallis [9] (Eq. 13) were selected. The results obtained from these equations are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Theoretical rise velocity of Taylor bubbles in a pipe.

Correlation	Theoretical velocity (mm/s)	Deviation from experimental value (%)
Brown (Eq. 9)	268	-1.1
Wallis (Eq. 13)	293	8.1

As observed in Table 3, equations 9 and 13 predict satisfactorily the rise velocity of a Taylor bubble.

Figure 2 shows three video frames of a Taylor bubble. Some structural characteristics can be noted: a hemispherical nose, a cylindrical air body surrounded by a thick liquid film and a flat bottom. The bubble's bottom is trailed by a thin wavy sheath of air entrained into the liquid. This sheath breaks into small bubbles, which are reabsorbed by the Taylor bubble. It is interesting to note that almost none of these small bubbles are left behind the Taylor bubble.

Figure 2. Frames of a rising Taylor bubble in a pipe.

Rise velocity of Taylor bubbles in an annulus

The measured rise velocities and its corrected values due to air expansion of four Taylor bubbles in an annulus are given in Table 4. This bubbles were formed injecting 300, 250, 200 and 100 cm³ of air inside an inverted cup.

Table 4. Experimental rise velocity of Taylor bubbles in an annulus.

Injected air volume ^c (cm ³)	Length (mm)	Experimental velocity (mm/s)	
		Measured ± 6	Corrected ^d
300	150	311	307
250	130	312	308
200	110	311	309
100	70	311	309

^c Absolute pressure 88.7 kPa. Test temperature , 21.0°C.

^d Experimental velocity corrected by air expansion effect.

The average rise velocity of a Taylor bubble in an annulus, at the present study conditions is 308 mm/s.

The influence of the inner cylinder on the rise velocity has been considered by some authors [2, 15, 16, 17, 18], but a comprehensive model tying all the relevant variables is still missing in the literature. Nevertheless, an attempt to use equations 9 and 13 is made using five different definitions of the annular space characteristic dimension. These definitions are:

1. Pipe diameter, D .
2. Hydraulic diameter, D_H :

$$D_H = D - d. \quad (19)$$

3. Equiperiphery diameter, D_{EP} [18]:

$$D_{EP} = D + d. \quad (20)$$

4. Equivalent diameter, D_E [16]:

$$D_E = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\pi(D+d)}{2} + \frac{(D-d)}{2} \right] = \frac{D}{4} \left[(\pi+1) + \frac{d}{D}(\pi-1) \right]. \quad (22)$$

Table 5 shows the results for each case. The best model is Eq. 9 combined with D_{EP} . The same equation yields a satisfactory result using D_E . Wallis's equation (Eq. 13) also provides a good prediction when the equivalent diameter D_E or D is used as the characteristic dimension.

Table 5. Theoretical rise velocity of Taylor bubbles in an annulus.

Characteristic dimension	Theoretical velocity (mm/s)		Deviation from experimental value (%)	
	Brown (Eq. 9)	Wallis (Eq. 13)	Brown (Eq. 9)	Wallis (Eq. 13)
D	268	291	-13.0	-5.5
D_H	213	212	-30.8	-31.2
D_{EP}	314	343	1.9	11.4
D_E	298	326	-3.2	5.8

An odd feature is that the experimental rise velocity in the annulus is 14% higher than that in the round tube. This result implies that the internal rod do have a significant effect on the bubble kinematics. So, the use of solely D as a characteristic dimension for the annulus is not advised. Neither is the hydraulic diameter D_H . The use of this popular concept points at the opposite way because when used with either model, Eq. 9 or Eq. 13, the rise velocity in an annulus will result in a lower value than in a pipe, which clearly contradicts the experiments.

Figure 3 shows three video frames of a Taylor bubble rising through an annulus. Figure 3a portraits the front of the bubble and 3b the back. The most interesting feature is perhaps the fact that the bubble wraps partially the internal cylinder, allowing the existence of a liquid channel flowing downwards. This behavior has been noted before [16, 17]. The frontal view (Fig. 3a) reveals a flatter bubble nose compared with the bubble in a round pipe. Again, the falling film attached to the pipe wall can be seen, but now another film is also present attached to the rod. The bubble's bottom is flat and static. A thin sheath of air also appears but now with a smooth, bubbleless, completely stable shape.

Figure 3. Taylor bubble rising in an annulus.

Rise velocity of cap bubbles in a circular pipe

Several bubble volumes were tested in order to study the rise velocity behavior of cap bubbles. Table 6 shows the measurement results.

These bubbles were classified using the shape regime map depicted by Bhaga and Weber [3]. It is remarkable that the rise velocity of the skirted wavy bubble of 40.8 cm³ is equal to that of the bigger Taylor bubble in a pipe. The subsequent smaller bubbles have lower rise velocities.

Table 6. Experimental rise velocity of cap bubbles in a pipe.

Bubble type	Bubble volume ^c (cm ³ ± 0.2)	Equivalent radius, R _b (mm)	Experimental velocity (mm/s ± 6)
Skirted wavy	40.8	21.4	270
	27.2	18.7	264
Skirted smooth	18.1	16.3	263
Ellipsoidal cap	16.3	15.7	258
	9.1	13.0	244
	5.4	10.9	227
Oblate ellipsoidal cap	0.7	5.6	123

^c Bubble volume inside the liquid column. Absolute pressure 97.8 kPa. Test temperature 22.0°C.

Figure 4. Cap bubbles in a circular pipe.

Calculations were made to predict the rise velocity of these cap bubbles using the methods proposed by Peebles and Garber [1], Harmathy [6], Clift *et al.* [7] graphical correlation and Jamialahmadi *et al.* [8]. See Figure 5.

Figure 5. Comparison of measured bubble rise velocities with calculated values.

The rise velocity obtained with the Peebles and Garber's equation is 162 mm/s and with Harmathy's correlation, 209 mm/s. Both equations are independent of the bubble size. But the experimental rise velocity shows a different behavior. The velocity increases with the bubble size.

When a bubble rises in a tube, its velocity is expected to be lower than the value in an infinite medium. However, it is remarkable that the experimental velocities obtained in this study are larger than the theoretical velocities obtained with equations of Peebles and Garber and Harmathy, except for the smallest bubble (5.6 mm of equivalent radius).

The values obtained with the equation of Davies and Taylor [5] are up to 89 % larger than the experimental ones. The velocities estimated with the Clift *et al.* [7] graphical correlation and Jamialahmadi's [8] correlation were bigger than the experimental ones except for the smallest bubble. This correlations over estimate the rise velocity since the wall effects were neglected.

Equation 7 was used to correct the predicted rise velocity due to the wall effect. Figure 6 shows this result compared with the experimental velocity.

Jamialahmadi's correlation yields the smaller errors, less than 9%. For the smallest bubble the correction due to wall effect must not be applied because the Jamialahmadi's correlation underestimates the rise velocity for this bubble size. Therefore, it is necessary to review the range of applicability of Eq. 7.

Figure 6. Bubble rise velocities corrected by wall effect.

Rise velocity of cap bubbles in an annulus

Table 7 shows the measured rise velocity of five bubble sizes and the values predicted by Eq. 4. The error of the predicted value relative to the experimental one ranges from 26 up to 53 %.

Table 7. Cap bubbles rise velocity in an annulus.

Bubble volume ^f (cm ³ ± 0.2)	Equivalent radius, R _b (mm)	Rise velocity, (mm/s)		Error (%)
		Experimental ± 8	Theoretical (Eq. 4)	
40.9	21.4	293	447	53
18.2	16.3	270	380	41
16.4	15.8	272	373	37
9.1	13.0	249	325	31
0.6	11.0	224	282	26

^f Bubble volume inside the liquid column. Absolute pressure 97.6 kPa. Test temperature 21.5 °C.

There is no correlation available in the literature to predict the rise velocity of a cap bubble rising through an annulus. Nevertheless, Eq. 4 was used to calculate the rise velocity and the values were corrected by the Eq. 7. These calculations were made using four definitions of characteristic dimension: pipe diameter, hydraulic diameter, equiperiphery diameter and the equivalent area. The results are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Theoretical velocity of cap bubbles for different characteristic dimensions.

Equivalent radius, R _b (mm±0.2)	Theoretical velocity (Eq. 4) corrected with Eq. 7, (mm/s)				Deviation from the experimental value (%)			
	D	D _H	D _{EP}	D _E	D	D _H	D _{EP}	D _E
21.4	289	219	332	319	-1.4	-25.3	13.3	8.9
16.3	280	227	312	302	3.7	-15.9	15.6	11.9
15.7	279	227	309	300	2.6	-16.5	13.6	10.3
12.9	261	221	284	277	4.8	-11.2	14.1	11.2
10.9	240	208	257	252	7.1	-7.1	14.7	12.5

Table 8 shows that the smaller errors correspond to the calculus using the pipe diameter, with an average error 4%.

It is important to note that the rise velocity of a cap bubble in the annulus is slightly larger (2 to 8%) a bubble with the same volume in a circular pipe.

Figure 7 shows images of the front and back of a cap bubble in an annulus. The bubble exhibits an elliptical cap shape and wraps partially the rod. A map for bubble shape regime is a fundamental knowledge still missing for the annular configuration.

Figure 7. Cap bubbles in an annulus.

5. NOMENCLATURE

- d rod diameter, m .
- D pipe inside diameter m .
- D_E equivalent diameter, m .
- d_e diameter of the equivalent volume of a sphere, m .
- D_{EP} equiperiphery diameter, m .
- D_H hydraulic diameter, m .
- Fr Froude number.
- $Eö$ Eötvös number.
- g gravity acceleration, m/s^2 .
- k dimensionless parameter.
- N properties group, defined by Eq. 10, m^{-1} .
- n coefficient function of N_f .
- N_f viscosity inverse number.
- R tube radius, m .
- R_b spherical bubble equivalent radius, m .
- R_c radius of curvature at bubble top, m .
- Re Reynolds number
- u terminal rise velocity of the bubble in a restricted medium, m/s .
- u' terminal rise velocity of the bubble in a restricted medium without gas expansion correction, m/s .
- u_∞ terminal single bubble rise velocity in an infinite medium, m/s .
- u_∞^{sp} terminal single spherical bubble rise velocity, m/s .
- u_∞^w terminal single wavy bubble rise velocity, m/s .
- σ interfacial tension, N/m .
- μ_l liquid viscosity, $Pa.s$.
- μ_g gas viscosity, $Pa.s$.
- ρ_l liquid density, kg/m^3 .
- ρ_g gas density, kg/m^3 .

6. CONCLUSIONS

For the conditions of the present study, the Brown's correlation predicts accurately the rise velocity of a Taylor bubble in a pipe and can be also used together with the equiperiphery diameter to predict the rise velocity of a Taylor bubble in an annulus.

The rise velocity of a cap bubble in an annular space can be predicted correcting the wall effect on the values obtained with Jamialahmadi's equation using the pipe diameter.

Finally, bubbles rise faster in an annular space than in a circular one.

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